

From migrants to residents – shifting behaviour in migratory birds to withstand global change (MigRes)

Version 1

Description

Data collection, storage and availability of the dataset of demography and migration data of Common Starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*)

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

From migrants to residents –
shifting behaviour in migratory
birds to withstand global
change (MigRes)
(lcs_____::lzp-2023/1-0233)/
No lzp-2023/1-0233

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: From migrants to residents – shifting behaviour in migratory birds to withstand global change (MigRes)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: From migrants to residents – shifting behaviour in migratory birds to withstand global change (MigRes) (lcs_____:lzp-2023/1-0233)

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Breeding and migration data on Common Starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*) in Latvia

The study will be recording the breeding and migration data of the Common Starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*): timing of breeding onset, egg laying, clutch size, hatching and fledgling success in all nest boxes as well as capturing and ringing adult breeders and their offspring to estimate local return rates, apparent survival, and recruitment. As well as data acquired by geolocators

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data are collected for the study of interactions between breeding and migration decisions on short-distance migrant species - Common Starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*). Data are collected in nest boxes, where Common Starlings do breed and by the multi-sensor geolocators employed on adult Common Starlings breeding in those nest-boxes.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Observation data
- Other

geocator data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV

- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The geolocators are new technology, it has not been applied to short-distance migrant species like Common Starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*)

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Phenological data might be useful for observing the probable shifts in spring onset in Europe.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

Sample collection sites and dates, species names

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the study is published by our group

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://spibirds.org/en>

[https://www.movebank.org/cms/webapp?
gwt_fragment=page=studies,path=study4343615686](https://www.movebank.org/cms/webapp?gwt_fragment=page=studies,path=study4343615686)

Similar data are stored in these platforms.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

no specific software

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

csv

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Scientific names of the species and standard place coordinates will be used

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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